

Deliverable report for

Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling

Project 101058632

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1 TABLE OF CONTENTS

2	Abbreviations and Acronyms	4
3	Executive Summary	5
4	Introduction	6
4.1	Concentrates obtained in the various countries	6
4.1.1	Austria	6
4.1.2	Germany	6
4.1.3	Portugal.....	6
4.1.4	Slovakia	6
4.1.5	Spain.....	6
5	Annex I – Details of the concentrate nature and quantity delivered to WP3.....	7
	Austria.....	8
	Germany	23
	Portugal	33
	Slovakia	40
	Spain.....	42

2 ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
WP(s)	Work Package(s)

3 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The document below presents a summary of the mineral concentrates obtained within the work carried out in WP2 (Selection of mine waste sites; physical minerals separation and concentration) and the samples delivered to the WP3 (Materials modelling and processing) partners of the START consortium, to be used in the implementation of the activities of Task 3.2 - Mechanochemical synthesis of mineral-derived sulphide p-type materials and of Task 3.4 - Production of mineral-derived sulphide p-type materials by rapid casting production process. The summary of the concentrates delivered can be seen in the annex of this document.

4 INTRODUCTION

The minerals obtained at each chosen mining site implied unique mineral separation procedures for each site resulting from the mineralogical associations and paragenesis encountered. The concentration procedures and treatment of the samples have been dealt with in detail in the previous deliverable D2.2 (Treatment and separation of suitable minerals), which was submitted in month 14.

4.1 CONCENTRATES OBTAINED IN THE VARIOUS COUNTRIES

Below is a summary of the number of concentrates obtained for delivery to WP3. The full details are available in Annex I.

4.1.1 Austria

- 7 sites selected.
- Concentrates obtained from 3 sites.

4.1.2 Germany

- 5 sites selected.
- Concentrates obtained from 5 sites.
- 5 concentrates delivered.

4.1.3 Portugal

- 3 sites selected.
- Concentrates obtained from 3 sites.
- 3 concentrates delivered.

4.1.4 Slovakia

- 1 site selected.
- Concentrates obtained from 1 site.
- 1 (composite) concentrates delivered.

4.1.5 Spain

- 21 sites selected.
- Concentrates obtained from 3 sites.
- 3 concentrates delivered.

5 ANNEX I – DETAILS OF THE CONCENTRATE NATURE AND QUANTITY DELIVERED TO WP3

AUSTRIA

		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET				Date: 01.09.2022 Country: Austria	
Sample ID: ATANTO006		Coordinates: (EPSG:3035)		X: 4452462.21	Y: 2694713.11		
Sampler		Ch. Auer, P. Lipiarski, S. Pfeiderer, R. Strauss					
Organization		Geosphere Austria, GEO Unterweissacher					
Mine name		Schwaz – Mining district Falkenstein					
Deposit type		Ag- and Hg-bearing tetrahedrite, together with barite					
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine		X	
Sample type		Spotted	X	Well		Channel	
Simple		Composite	X	Number of sub samples			
STATE		Oxidised		X		Fresh	
Mine waste type		Waste rock			Waste rock dump		X
		Tailings			Stockpiles		
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		About 12.000 Square meters					
Material size		Sand		Gravel	X	Stones	X
Mineralogy		Fahlore, Nickelskutterudite, Malachite, Chalcopryite, Stibnite, Azurite, Mercury, Devilline, Chalcostibite, Spangolite, Covellite, Realgar, Cinnabar, Tyrolite					
Photos		<p style="text-align: center;">Figure 1: Sample ATANTO006</p>					
Separation Methodology used		Sample milled					
Final concentrate mass (kg)		To be delivered					
Comments		The Austrian samples were successfully taken by Geosphere and Geo Unterweissacher. The Montanuniversität Leoben crushed those samples and sieved them into different fractions. First step in the enrichment process was, to separate the heavy minerals (fahlore) from the host rock. But the shacking table, was not					

	<p>successful. The reason is, that the marble host rock has nearly the same density as the fahlore.</p> <p>The second attempt was a wet process through EMS (electromagnetic separation). Also, with no positive result. It looks like the magnetic forces are too weak to enrich the ore. Our partner, the BGR, has a permanent magnetic separator at its disposal. Having the material separated into several grain size fractions, the ore could indeed be enriched in the magnetic fraction. To concentrate it further, gravity separation could successfully be applied for specific grain size fractions. In order to concentrate the ore from the <100µm fraction, another step must be taken. This could be done by flotation of the samples.</p>
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		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET			Date: 30.08.2022 Country: Austria	
Sample ID: ATGISH003		Coordinates: (EPSG:3035) X: 4522849.07		Y: 2704632.26		
Sampler		Ch. Auer, P. Lipiarski, S. Pfeleiderer, T. Unterweissacher, R. Strauss				
Organization		Geosphere Austria, GEO Unterweissacher				
Mine name		Barbarastollen Gipsschacht				
Deposit type		Polymetallic Cu-Ni-Co-Hg-Ag				
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine		X
Sample type		Spotted		X	Well	
Simple		Composite		Channel		
STATE		Oxidised		X		Fresh
Mine waste type		Waste rock		X		Waste rock dump
		Tailings				Stockpiles
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		Samples from inside the mine. Dimension cannot be estimated.				
Material size		Sand		Gravel		X
				Stones		X
Mineralogy		Dominant ore minerals include tennantite, chalcopyrite, cinnabar, galena, bornite and magnesite				
Photos		<p>Figure 1: Sample ATGISH003</p>				
Separation Methodology used		Sample milled				
Final concentrate mass (kg)		To be delivered				
Comments		The Austrian samples were successfully taken by Geosphere and Geo Unterweissacher. The Montanuniversität Leoben crushed those samples and sieved them into different fractions. First step in the enrichment process was, to separate the heavy minerals (fahlore) from the host rock. But the shacking table, was not				

	<p>successful. The reason is, that the marble host rock has nearly the same density as the fahlore.</p> <p>The second attempt was a wet process through EMS (electromagnetic separation). Also, with no positive result. It looks like the magnetic forces are too weak to enrich the ore. Our partner, the BGR, has a permanent magnetic separator at its disposal, which, however, does not work for this sample. The ore minerals and most of the other minerals go together into the magnetic fraction. In order to concentrate it further, a further step must be taken. This could be done by flotation of the samples.</p>
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		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET				Date: 31.08.2022 Country: Austria			
Sample ID: ATMAHE002		Coordinates: (EPSG:3035)		X: 4522920.95	Y: 2704644.47				
Sampler		Ch. Auer, P. Lipiarski, S. Pfeleiderer, T. Unterweissacher, R. Strauss							
Organization		Geosphere Austria, GEO Unterweissacher							
Mine name		Barbarastollen Maria Heimsuchung							
Deposit type		Polymetallic Cu-Ni-Co-Hg-Ag							
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine		X			
Sample type		Spotted		X	Well		Channel		
Simple		Composite		X	Number of sub samples				
STATE		Oxidised		X		Fresh			
Mine waste type		Waste rock		X		Waste rock dump			
		Tailings				Stockpiles			
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		Samples from inside the mine. Dimension cannot be estimated.							
Material size		Sand		Gravel		X	Stones		X
Mineralogy		Dominant ore minerals include tennantite, chalcopryrite, cinnabar, galena, bornite and magnesite							
Photos		<p>Figure 1: Sample ATMAHE002</p>							
Separation Methodology used		Sample milled							
Final concentrate mass (kg)		To be delivered							
Comments		The Austrian samples were successfully taken by Geosphere and Geo Unterweissacher. The Montanuniversität Leoben crushed those samples and sieved them into different fractions. First step in the enrichment process was, to separate the heavy minerals (fahlore) from the host rock. But the shacking table, was not							

	<p>successful. The reason is, that the marble host rock has nearly the same density as the fahlore.</p> <p>The second attempt was a wet process through EMS (electromagnetic separation). Also, with no positive result. It looks like the magnetic forces are too weak to enrich the ore. Our partner, the BGR, has a permanent magnetic separator at its disposal, which, however, does not work for this sample. The ore minerals and most of the other minerals go together into the magnetic fraction. In order to concentrate it further, a further step must be taken. This could be done by flotation of the samples.</p>
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		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET			Date: 30.08.2022 Country: Austria	
Sample ID: ATNOEK001		Coordinates: (EPSG:3035)		X: 4523264.98	Y: 2705747.89	
Sampler		Ch. Auer, P. Lipiarski, S. Pfeiderer, R. Strauss, T. Unterweissacher				
Organization		Geosphere Austria, GEO Unterweissacher				
Mine name		Leogang-Noeckelberg				
Deposit type		Polymetallic Cu-Ni-Co-Hg-Ag				
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine		X
Sample type		Spotted	X	Well	Channel	
Simple	Composite	X	Number of sub samples			
STATE		Oxidised		X		Fresh
Mine waste type		Waste rock		Waste rock dump		X
		Tailings		Stockpiles		
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		ca. 160x110m				
Material size		Sand	Gravel	X	Stones	X
Mineralogy		Dominant ore minerals include tennantite, chalcopyrite, cinnabar, galena, bornite and magnesite				
Photos		<p style="text-align: center;">Figure 1: Sample ATNOEK001</p>				
Separation Methodology used		Sample milled				
Final concentrate mass (kg)		To be delivered				
Comments		The Austrian samples were successfully taken by Geosphere and Geo Unterweissacher. The Montanuniversität Leoben crushed those samples and sieved them into different fractions. First step in the enrichment process was, to separate the heavy minerals (fahlore) from the host rock. But the shacking table, was not successful. The				

	<p>reason is, that the marble host rock has nearly the same density as the fahlore.</p> <p>The second attempt was a wet process through EMS (electromagnetic separation). Also, with no positive result. It looks like the magnetic forces are too weak to enrich the ore. Our partner, the BGR, has a permanent magnetic separator at its disposal, which, however, does not work for this sample. The ore minerals and most of the other minerals go together into the magnetic fraction. However, having the material separated into multiple grain size fractions, the ore can be separated with a wet shaking table for specific grain size fractions. In order to concentrate the ore in the < 100 µm fraction, another step must be taken. This could be done by flotation of the samples.</p>
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		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET			Date: 01.09.2022 Country: Austria	
Sample ID: ATSAPO004		Coordinates: (EPSG:3035) X: 4452038.11		Y: 2694685.81		
Sampler		Ch. Auer, P. Lipiarski, S. Pfeleiderer, R. Strauss				
Organization		Geosphere Austria, GEO Unterweissacher				
Mine name		Schwaz – Mining district Falkenstein				
Deposit type		Ag- and Hg-bearing tetrahedrite, together with barite				
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine		X
Sample type		Spotted		X	Well	
Simple		Composite		Channel		
STATE		Oxidised		X		Fresh
Mine waste type		Waste rock		Waste rock dump		
		Tailings		X		Stockpiles
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		About 49.000 Square meters				
Material size		Sand		X		Gravel
Mineralogy		Dominant ore minerals include Ag- and Hg-bearing tetrahedrite, together with barite				
Photos		<p style="text-align: center;">Figure 1: Sample ATSAPO004</p>				
Separation Methodology used		Sample milled				
Final concentrate mass (kg)		To be delivered				
Comments		The Austrian samples were successfully taken by Geosphere and Geo Unterweissacher. The Montanuniversität Leoben crushed those samples and sieved them into different fractions. First step in the enrichment process was, to separate the heavy minerals (fahlore) from				

	<p>the host rock. But the shacking table, was not successful. The reason is, that the marble host rock has nearly the same density as the fahlore. The second attempt was a wet process through EMS (electromagnetic separation). Also, with no positive result. It looks like the magnetic forces are too weak to enrich the ore. Our partner, the BGR, has a permanent magnetic separator at its disposal. The ore can indeed be enriched to some extend in the magnetic fraction. In order to concentrate it further, a further step must be taken. This could be done by flotation of the samples.</p>
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		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET			Date: 01.09.2022 Country: Austria	
Sample ID: ATSAPO005		Coordinates: (EPSG:3035)		X: 4452058.04		Y: 2694702.90
Sampler		Ch. Auer, P. Lipiarski, S. Pfeleiderer, R. Strauss				
Organization		Geosphere Austria, GEO Unterweissacher				
Mine name		Schwaz – Mining district Falkenstein				
Deposit type		Ag- and Hg-bearing tetrahedrite, together with barite				
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine		X
Sample type		Spotted	X	Well	Channel	
Simple		Composite	X	Number of sub samples		
STATE		Oxidised		X		Fresh
Mine waste type		Waste rock		Waste rock dump		
		Tailings		X		Stockpiles
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		About 49.000 Square meters				
Material size		Sand	X	Gravel	Stones	
Mineralogy		Dominant ore minerals include Ag- and Hg-bearing tetrahedrite, together with barite				
Photos		<p style="text-align: center;">Figure 1: Sample ATSAPO005</p>				
Separation Methodology used		Sample milled				
Final concentrate mass (kg)		To be delivered				
Comments		The Austrian samples were successfully taken by Geosphere and Geo Unterweissacher. The Montanuniversität Leoben crushed those samples and sieved them into different fractions. First step in the				

	<p>enrichment process was, to separate the heavy minerals (fahlore) from the host rock. But the shacking table, was not successful. The reason is, that the marble host rock has nearly the same density as the fahlore.</p> <p>The second attempt was a wet process through EMS (electromagnetic separation). Also, with no positive result. It looks like the magnetic forces are too weak to enrich the ore. Our partner, the BGR, has a permanent magnetic separator at its disposal. The ore can indeed be enriched to some extend in the magnetic fraction. In order to concentrate it further, a further step must be taken. This could be done by flotation of the samples.</p>
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		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET				Date: 02.09.2022 Country: Austria	
Sample ID: ATSIGM007		Coordinates: (EPSG:3035)		X: 4453347.91	Y: 2694663.02		
Sampler		Ch. Auer, P. Lipiarski, S. Pfeleiderer					
Organization		Geosphere Austria					
Mine name		Schwaz – Mining district Falkenstein					
Deposit type		Ag- and Hg-bearing tetrahedrite, together with barite					
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine		X	
Sample type		Spotted	X	Well		Channel	
Simple		Composite	X	Number of sub samples			
STATE		Oxidised		X		Fresh	
Mine waste type		Waste rock			Waste rock dump		X
		Tailings			Stockpiles		
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		About 49.000 Square meters					
Material size		Sand		Gravel	X	Stones	X
Mineralogy		Fahlore, Nickelskutterudite, Malachite, Chalcopyrite, Stibnite, Azurite, Mercury, Devilline, Chalcostibite, Spangolite, Covellite, Realgar, Cinnabar, Tyrolite					
Photos		<p>Figure 1: Sample ATSIGM007</p>					
Separation Methodology used		Sample milled					
Final concentrate mass (kg)		To be delivered					
Comments		The Austrian samples were successfully taken by Geosphere and Geo Unterweissacher. The Montanuniversität Leoben crushed those samples and sieved them into different fractions. First step in the enrichment process was, to separate the heavy minerals (fahlore)					

	<p>from the host rock. But the shacking table, was not successful. The reason is, that the marble host rock has nearly the same density as the fahlore.</p> <p>The second attempt was a wet process through EMS (electromagnetic separation). Also, with no positive result. It looks like the magnetic forces are too weak to enrich the ore. Our partner, the BGR, has a permanent magnetic separator at its disposal. Having the material separated into several grain size fractions, the ore could indeed be enriched in the magnetic fraction. In order to concentrate it further, gravity separation could successfully be applied for specific grain size fractions. In order to concentrate the ore in the <100µm fraction, another step must be taken. This could be done by flotation of the samples.</p>
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GERMANY

		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET				Date: 2015 Country: Germany	
Sample ID: GER/BT/001/RSCP5_1		Coordinates: (ETRS89)		X: 10.464828		Y: 51.902923	
Sampler		REWITA project consortium					
Organization		CUTEC, PPM, HMG, STÖBICH, PDV, BIG, TUC					
Mine name		Rammelsberg mine (Harz Mountains, Germany)					
Deposit type		SEDEX type deposit (black smoker) of Devonian age, folded and compressed during development of the Harz.					
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine		X	
Sample type		Spotted		Well		X	
Simple		X		Number of sub samples		1 (sulphide concentrate)	
STATE		Oxidised		Fresh		X	
Mine waste type		Waste rock		Waste rock dump			
		Tailings		X		Stockpiles	
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		Bollrich tailings pond: 600,000 m ² (approx. 7 Mio. t)					
Material size		Sand		X (silt-clay)		Gravel	
						Stones	
Mineralogy		Average tailings composition: 55% carbonates and silicates, 25% barite, and 20% sulphides (Römer and Goldmann, 2019). The sulphide concentrate consists of pyrite, barite, carbonate, muscovite, chlorite, galena, sphalerite, feldspar, quartz. Minor contents of chalcopyrite, gypsum, and pyrrhotite.					
Photos		<p>Figure 2: Sample GER/BT/001/RSCP5_1 (freeze-dried)</p>					

Separation Methodology used	Flotation
Final concentrate mass (kg)	0.6
Comments	<p>The tailings were sampled, analysed, and processed by the REWITA project consortium. A subsample of their sulphide concentrate was kindly made available for START. In this BMBF-funded project, drill cores from different depths and locations were collected from the Rammelsberg Bollrich tailings pond (Schirmer et al., 2017). Furthermore, a process scheme for the recovery and complete reprocessing of the Bollrich tailings material has been developed and tested at laboratory scale (Römer et al., 2018; Römer and Goldmann, 2019).</p> <p>References:</p> <p>Römer, F., Goldmann, D. (2019) Wiederaufbereitung eines bergbaulichen Abfalls im Harz – Wie aus Altlasten in Zukunft vielleicht Lagerstätten werden., CHEMKON 2019, 26, 66. DOI: 10.1002/ckon.201800080</p> <p>Römer, F., Binder, A., & Goldmann, D. (2018). Basic considerations for the reprocessing of sulfidic tailings using the example of the bollrich tailing ponds. World of Metallurgy - ERZMETALL, 71(3), 135-143. Retrieved from www.scopus.com</p> <p>Schirmer, T., Römer, F., Elwert, T., Goldmann, D., (2017) Characterization of tailings of the Rammelsberg ore deposit for a potential reprocessing. Proceedings of the 9th European Metallurgical conference, EMC 2017, 25-28 June 2017, www.scopus.com</p> <p>Project REWITA (funded by BMBF, 2015-2018): https://www.rewimet.de/aktivitaeten/projekte/rewita</p> <p>Project REMINTA (funded by BMBF, 2020–2023): https://www.reminta.de/</p>

		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET			Date: 2023 Country: Germany	
Sample ID: GER/PO1/002		Coordinates: (ETRS89)		X: Confidential		Y: Confidential
Sampler		third party (see comments below)				
Organization		third party (see comments below)				
Mine name		see comments below				
Deposit type		see comments below				
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine		
Sample type		Spotted		Well		Channel
Simple		Composite		X		Number of sub samples
STATE		Oxidised		Fresh		X
Mine waste type		Waste rock		Waste rock dump		
		Tailings		Stockpiles		
Dimension and geometry of mining waste						
Material size		Sand		Gravel		Stones
Mineralogy		Tennantite, chalcopyrite, chalcocite, pyrite, barite, quartz. Minor contents of tetrahedrite, covellite, digenite, an undetermined Cu-Ag- and Cu-Fe sulphide, barite, fluorite, and clay minerals (muscovite-illite).				
Photos						
Separation Methodology used		Crushing, milling, density separation, flotation				
Final concentrate mass (kg)		0.3				
Comments		This sample represents a natural fahlore-rich concentrate from German primary ore. About 300 grams of material have been provided for use in START by a third party under the condition, that the origin of the sample is not revealed.				

		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET				Date: Country: Germany	
		Sample ID: GER/PO2/Ro/006		Coordinates: (ETRS89) X: 8.355504		Y: 50.842833	
Sampler		The samples (tetrahedrite-rich ore) were obtained from the BGR geoscientific collections.					
Organization		BGR					
Mine name		Gottesgabe mine by Roth, Lahn-Dill-Kreis					
Deposit type		Vein-type ore deposit with fahlore-chalcopryrite in quartz					
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine		X	
Sample type		Spotted		Well		Channel	
Simple		Composite		Number of sub samples		3	
STATE		Oxidised		X		Fresh	
Mine waste type		Waste rock		Waste rock dump			
		Tailings		Stockpiles			
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		Unknown (mining site renatured and/or overgrown). Sampling was not permitted.					
Material size		Sand		Gravel		Stones	
Mineralogy		Tetrahedrite, quartz, and minor contents of goethite					
Photos							

Separation Methodology used	Crushing, magnetic separation, gravity separation
Final concentrate mass (kg)	0.8
Comments	This natural tetrahedrite-rich concentrate originates from primary ore samples that were obtained from the BGR geoscientific collections.

		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET			Date: Country: Germany	
Sample ID: GER/PO3/An/007		Coordinates: (ETRS89) X: 10.518603		Y: 51.710236		
Sampler		The samples (tetrahedrite-rich ore) were obtained from the BGR geoscientific collections.				
Organization		BGR				
Mine name		Ore district of Sankt Andreasberg (Harz); Samson mine				
Deposit type		Polymetallic vein-type ore deposit with fahlore in calcite/quartz				
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine	X	
Sample type		Spotted		Well		Channel
Simple	Composite	Number of sub samples			1	
STATE		Oxidised	X	Fresh	X	
Mine waste type		Waste rock			Waste rock dump	X
		Tailings			Stockpiles	
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		Several waste rock dumps, mostly re-cultivated/overgrown. Dump at St. Jacobsglücks mine: 10000 – 100000 m ³ .				
Material size		Sand		Gravel		Stones
Mineralogy		Tetrahedrite, quartz, and minor contents of goethite				
Photos						
Separation Methodology used		Crushing, magnetic separation, gravity separation				
Final concentrate mass (kg)		0.13				
Comments		This natural tetrahedrite concentrate originates from a primary ore sample that was obtained from the BGR geoscientific collections. Mining waste dumps around St Andreasberg have mostly been re-				

	<p>cultivated and/or are overgrown. Furthermore, mineral collectors have extensively searched any accessible dumps ever since mine closure. BGR has taken samples from three different waste rock dumps in this area (2011, ROBEHA project), and none of them showed elevated concentrations of copper or antimony. The Samson mine is still accessible.</p>
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		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET		Date: Country: Germany	
Sample ID: GER/PO4/Mü/008		Coordinates: (ETRS89) X: 8.035354		Y: 50.993386	
Sampler		The samples (tetrahedrite-rich ore) was obtained from the geoscientific collections of the TU Freiberg, Germany.			
Organization		BGR			
Mine name		A former mine by Littfeld, Kreis Siegen-Wittgenstein; Heinrichsseggen mine			
Deposit type		Vein-type ore deposit with fahlore in quartz			
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine	
Sample type		Spotted		Well	
Simple		Composite		Channel	
		Number of sub samples		1	
STATE		Oxidised		Fresh	
		X		X	
Mine waste type		Waste rock		Waste rock dump	
		Tailings		Stockpiles	
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		< 5000 m ³ .			
Material size		Sand		Gravel	
				Stones	
Mineralogy		Tetrahedrite, quartz, and minor contents of chalcopyrite and muscovite			
Photos					
Separation Methodology used		Crushing, magnetic separation			
Final concentrate mass (kg)		0.085			
Comments		This natural tetrahedrite concentrate originates from primary ore samples that were obtained from the geoscientific collections of the TU Freiberg. The small mining waste dump at the Heinrichsseggen			

	mine mainly consists of wall rock and minor amounts of vein minerals.
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PORTUGAL

		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET			Date: 15/11/2022 Country: Portugal	
Sample ID: PT/BRAN/001/A		Coordinates: (ETRS89)		X: 11148.71	Y: -234497.867	
Sampler		Igor Morais and Luís Albardeiro				
Organization		LNEG – Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia				
Mine name		Brançanes mine				
Deposit type		Veins – Quartz vein N40°E; 80SE				
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine	X	
Sample type		Spotted	X	Well	Channel	
Simple	X	Composite		Number of sub samples		
STATE		Oxidized	X	Fresh		
Mine waste type		Waste rock		Waste rock dump		X
		Tailings		Stockpiles		
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		Small				
Material size		Sand		Gravel	Stones	X
Mineralogy		Quartz, chalcopyrite, pyrite, carbonates, azurite, covellite				
Photos						

Separation Methodology used	Sample milled (only)
Final concentrate mass (kg)	6.1
Comments	

		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET				Date: 15/11/2022 Country: Portugal		
Sample ID: PT/BARR/001/A		Coordinates: (ETRS89)		X: 18753.299		Y: -238839.436		
Sampler		Igor Morais and Luís Albardeiro						
Organization		LNEG – Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia						
Mine name		Barrigão mine						
Deposit type		Veins – two systems of quartz veins associated with struck slips						
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine		X		
Sample type		Spotted	X	Well	Channel			
Simple	X	Composite	Number of sub samples					
STATE		Oxidized		X		Fresh		
Mine waste type		Waste rock		Waste rock dump		X		
		Tailings		Stockpiles				
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		Medium						
Material size		Sand	Gravel	Stones	X			
Mineralogy		Chalcopyrite, tennantite, tetrahedrite, and pyrite, with minor or rare arsenopyrite, löllingite, sphalerite, native bismuth, and an undetermined Cu–Sn–Ge-sulphide; quartz and carbonates (Reiser et al., 2010)						
Photos								

Separation Methodology used	Sample milled (only)
Final concentrate mass (kg)	8.8
Comments	The ore samples revealed anomalous Sn and Ge contents with an average of 320 and 61 ppm, respectively, ranging between 16 and 872 ppm for Sn and 4 and 280 ppm for Ge.

		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET			Date: 15/09/2022 Country: Portugal	
Sample ID: PT/NC/001/A		Coordinates: (ETRS89)	X: 14581.949	Y: -232446.128		
Sampler		Igor Morais and Luís Albardeiro				
Organization		LNEG – Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia				
Mine name		Neves-Corvo mine				
Deposit type		VMS – 7 ore bodies with high grades of Cu and Zn				
Mine Status		Working Mine	X	Abandoned Mine		
Sample type		Spotted	X	Well	Channel	
Simple	X	Composite		Number of sub samples		
STATE		Oxidized		Fresh	X	
Mine waste type		Waste rock		Waste rock dump		
		Tailings		Stockpiles		
Dimension and geometry of mining waste						
Material size		Sand		Gravel	Stones	X
Mineralogy		Chalcopyrite, pyrite, tetrahedrite, quartz, jarosite, sulphur, melanterite, sphalerite, stannite				
Photos						

Separation Methodology used	Sample milled (only)
Final concentrate mass (kg)	6.4
Comments	Due to the access to the mine underground works being limited and intermittent, a total of 700 kg of sample were collected.

SLOVAKIA

		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET			Date: 16/11/2022 Country: Slovakia	
Sample ID: SK/RV/001/A		Coordinates: (ETRS89-TM34 (E, N))		X: 466221 m	Y: 5391602 m	
Sampler		Kubač, Kúšik				
Organization		ŠGÚDŠ				
Mine name		Mária mine				
Deposit type		Early Paleozoic metasedimentary/metavolcanitic				
Mine Status		Working Mine	X	Abandoned Mine		
Sample type		Spotted		Well		Channel
Simple		Composite	X	Number of sub samples	13	
STATE		Oxidised		Fresh	X	
Mine waste type		Waste rock		Waste rock dump		
		Tailings		Stockpiles X		
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		Square meters				
Material size		Sand		Gravel		Stones X
Mineralogy		Siderite and quartz–sulphide mineralization: The most abundant ore minerals are tetrahedrite, chalcopyrite, pyrite and arsenopyrite. Brittle, steel-grey coloured tetrahedrite, which is the most important ore mineral, is spatially controlled by the older siderite that is in the form of reticulated veins and clusters. A more brittle tetrahedrite variety with steel blue colour and high metallic lustre is usually enriched by Cu, Ag, Bi, Sb and Hg. A darker low lustre variety contains more Zn and Fe.				
Photos						
Separation Methodology used		Sample milled, magnetic separation, electromagnetic separation				
Final concentrate mass (kg)		9.96				
Comments		Whole sample handled as 13 subsamples.				

SPAIN

		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET			Date: 15/09/2022 Country: Spain	
Sample ID: ES C0 01		Coordinates: (ETRS89) X: 320760		Y: 4796689		
Sampler		E. Boixereu, R. Jiménez, P. Adánez and C. Fernández-Leyva				
Organization		IGME-CSIC				
Mine name		El Coriellu				
Deposit type		The mineralisation corresponds to a low temperature (90-130°C) hydrothermal deposit. Quartz pockets and phylloclasts included in the Mountain Limestone (Upper Carboniferous)				
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine		X
Sample type		Spotted		Well		Channel
Simple	X	Composite		Number of sub samples		
STATE		Oxidised		X		Fresh
Mine waste type		Waste rock			Waste rock dump	
		Tailings			Stockpiles	
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		500 m ³ (a part of the waste dump is inside the mine itself, so it could be larger)				
Material size		Sand		Gravel		Stones X
Mineralogy		Tetrahedrite (Azurite, Quartz)				
Photos						

<p>Separation Methodology used</p>	<p>Gravity separation, Magnetic separation</p>
<p>Final concentrate mass (kg)</p>	<p>3.35</p>
<p>Comments</p>	<p>Samples from the dump with the highest tetrahedrite content were selected. Thus, the sample content is not representative of the total grade of the heap.</p>

		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET				Date: 15/09/2022 Country: Spain	
Sample ID: ESDE001		Coordinates: (ETRS89)		X: 344425		Y: 4798219	
Sampler		E. Boixereu, R. Jiménez, P. Adánez and C. Fernández-Leyva					
Organization		IGME-CSIC					
Mine name		Delfina					
Deposit type		The mineralisation corresponds to a low temperature (90-130°C) hydrothermal deposit embedded in the Carboniferous limestones of the Picos de Europa formation.					
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine		X	
Sample type		Spotted		X		Well	
Simple		Composite		X		Number of sub samples	
STATE		Oxidised		X		Fresh	
Mine waste type		Waste rock		Waste rock dump		X	
		Tailings		Stockpiles			
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		6000 m ³ (a part of the waste dump is inside the mine itself, so it could be larger)					
Material size		Sand		Gravel		Stones	
Mineralogy		Tetrahedrite (Chrysocoll, Tyrolite, Azurite, Muscovite, Quartz, Chalcopyrite)					
Photos							

<p>Separation Methodology used</p>	<p>Gravity separation (Wilfley table), Magnetic separation (Frantz)</p>
<p>Final concentrate mass (kg)</p>	<p>1.21</p>
<p>Comments</p>	<p>Samples from the dump with the highest tetrahedrite content were selected. Thus, the sample content is not representative of the total grade of the heap.</p>

		MINING WASTE SAMPLING PROTOCOL SAMPLE REGISTER SHEET			Date: 15/09/2022 Country: Spain	
Sample ID: ES TA 001		Coordinates: (ETRS89)		X: 625410	Y: 4476980	
Sampler		E. Boixereu, R. Jiménez, P. Adánez and C. Fernández-Leyva				
Organization		IGME-CSIC				
Mine name		Torres de Albarracín				
Deposit type		The mineralisation corresponds to a low temperature hydrothermal veins deposit. The mineralisation is hosted in quartzites of the Ordovician age. The mineralization consists mainly of Ag-rich Tetrahedrite (with Freibergite?) in Quartz and Siderite gangue.				
Mine Status		Working Mine		Abandoned Mine		X
Sample type		Spotted	X	Well	Channel	
Simple	Composite	X	Number of sub samples			
STATE		Oxidised		X		Fresh
Mine waste type		Waste rock		Waste rock dump		X
		Tailings		Stockpiles		
Dimension and geometry of mining waste		6000 m ³ + 3000 m ³				
Material size		Sand		Gravel	Stones	
Mineralogy		Tetrahedrite, Siderite, Galene, Quartz				
Photos						

Separation Methodology used	Gravity separation, Magnetic separation
Final concentrate mass (kg)	0.35
Comments	<p>Samples from the dump with the highest tetrahedrite content were selected. Thus, the sample content is not representative of the total grade of the heap. The separation of tetrahedrite and siderite was carried out in a high intensity magnet (SMAI band magnet), where the tetrahedrite remained in the non-magnetic fraction. This fraction was then subjected to gravity separation on a Wilfley table. In this way it was possible to separate a large part of the galena associated with the tetrahedrite. Finally, the tetrahedrite concentrate was obtained by separating the quartz and calcite with the Franz magnetic separator.</p>